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EXPORT PERFORMANCE AND OPERATIONAL PROBLEMS OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN INDIA- A CRITICAL EVALUATION

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Abstract

A Special Economic Zone (SEZ) is a geographical region that has economic laws that are more liberal than a country's typical economic laws. The category 'SEZ' covers a broad range of more specific zone types, including Free Trade Zones (FTZ), Export Processing Zones (EPZ), Free Zones (FZ), Industrial Estates (IE), Free Ports, Urban Enterprise Zones and others. Usually the goal of an SEZ structure is to increase foreign investment, to generate employment and to give boost to export. The most successful Special Economic Zone in China, [Shenzhen](#), has developed from a small village into a city with a population over 10 million within 20 years. Following the Chinese examples, Special Economic Zones have been established in several countries, including [Brazil](#), [India](#), [Iran](#), [Jordan](#), [Kazakhstan](#), [Pakistan](#), [the Philippines](#) .

This is hard to believe to people that India's SEZ's, a separate economic policy, would be successful like China to overcome shortcomings of fifteen years of liberalization in this country, namely low manufactured exports, 'jobless growth' and the failure to improve infrastructure. By changing patterns of both foreign and domestic investment in India, proponents of SEZ claim that it will create new islands of infrastructure and export promotion, all the while generating lakhs of jobs. SEZ's will be the driving force towards a new era of high growth, a new mantra for filling the 'gaps' in economic reforms.

In this research work researcher has made an attempt to explore the impact of Special Economic Zones on Export with comparison to Indian economy as whole and analyzed operational problems of SEZs during study period.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study has the following objectives:

1. To study the rationale of the SEZs in India.
2. To analyze export performance of SEZs with comparison to India as whole
3. To identify the operational problems of SEZs in India.

HYPOTHESES

During the study the following hypotheses have been tested.

1. Export Growth rate of SEZs and other than SEZs is equal to each other.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In the proposed study 20 SEZs were selected for the research work. The list of these SEZs is given below. Though by numbers these SEZs are just 20 but still play very vital role for the success of SEZ-policy of India.

To maintain the significance of the study and keep the data up to date by 31-March-2012 researcher also used the 9th category named "All Other SEZs".

- Santa Cruz (Maharashtra),
- Cochin (Kerala),
- Kandla (Gujarat),
- Surat (Gujarat),
- Visakhapatnam (Andhra Pradesh),
- Falta (West Bengal),
- Noida (Uttar Pradesh) and
- Chennai (Tamil Nadu)

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

All Selected SEZs mentioned in the scope of the study operational up to 31st March 2012 are studied in this research work. For the analysis purpose, their performance from 2002-03 to 2011-12 has been analyzed.

COLLECTION OF DATA

Researcher visited all selected SEZs for getting primary data through structured questionnaire and interview methods for identifying the operational problems of SEZs. As per the secondary data concerned researcher was very cautious about the authenticity and validity of data that's why he just believed mostly on government organizations and agencies.

To achieve the first objective of study researcher collected data from the parliamentary debate, planning commission suggestions to government and economist's criticism over the need of SEZ in India and experiences of other countries like as China and others.

To achieve the second objective of study researcher collected data mostly from government sources, by their official websites, on request from SEZs authorities and from other reliable studies. Information collected from different sources is analyzed and findings are presented accordingly to objectives.

To fulfill the third objective of study regarding the hassles of SEZs, the researcher contacted to promoters of SEZs and exporters, banking and financial institutions, government officials, employees of SEZs. To cover the third objective, researcher had to keep a continuous look over the performance of operational SEZs with export, FDI and Job opportunity.

SAMPLE DESIGN AND SIZE

Total number of units working as on 31st March 2012 in 20 selected SEZs is 2400. Researcher randomly selected just 200 units regardless any sector, size or other specific factor. From each selected SEZ of the research 10 numbers of units have been studied. Number of respondents from selected units are 400. From each unit 5 respondents were randomly selected.

The collection of primary data of the selected SEZs at various management levels of Firms have been selected through stratified random sampling. Thus for the study purpose all positioned rank/grade have been included in sample.

INSTRUMENTS OF DATA COLLECTION

Researcher prepared two set of questionnaire. One set of questionnaire was consisting questions for Investor’s Perspective. Under this set of questionnaire Researcher attempted to evaluate the following points:

- Physical infrastructure
- Infrastructure external to zone
- Social infrastructure
- Proximity to port
- Subsidies
- Regional development
- Tax concessions
- Governance of zones
- Policy regime
- Exception from industrial rules and regulations

While other set of questionnaire was for Firm’s Perspectives. Under this set of questionnaire Researcher attempted to evaluate the given below points:

- Ware house facility
- Container handing facility
- Efficiency of bank
- Transport facility for zone
- Roads leading to zones
- Transport within zone
- Logistics
- Port facility
- Internet facility
- Telephone facility

Data analysis and Interpretation

The whole of the findings of this study has been divided into following way:

EXPORT

The following Table-1 gives Export performance of SEZ and India.

Table-1 CAGR of SEZs and India to Export with SEZ to India Percentage

(Amount INR Cr)

Export	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	AGR
SEZ	8552.3	9189.55	10056.6	13853.9	18308.6	22839.5	34743.2	66627.7	4%
India	201356	209018	255137	293367	375340	456418	571779	655864	8%
% SEZ to India	4.25	4.40	3.94	4.72	4.88	5.00	6.08	10.16	

Sector-wise Value of Physical Exports from Special Economic Zones (SEZs) of India (2007-2008 to 2009-2010)			
(Rs. in Crore)			
Sector	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10
Biotech	159.45	832.65	456.48
Computer/Electronic Software	3985.26	16228.24	45784.26
Electronics Hardware	11121.33	13035.87	17417.39
Electronics	518.71	338.16	930.62
Engineering	1651.68	3089.34	4183.9
Gems and Jewellery	23006.07	33435.55	43828.97
Chemicals & Pharmaceuticals	1423.05	6386.21	73971.99
Handicrafts	30.33	38.13	49.77
Plastic and Rubber	657.66	343.07	688.24
Leather, Footwear and Sports goods	237.02	280.89	449.64
Food and Agro Industry	645.58	301.34	368.94
Non-conventional Energy	126.01	230.52	1398.09
Textiles and Garments	1316.61	2951.53	3313.24
Trading and Services	20866.97	18803.97	24884.22
Misc.	891.96	3393.55	2985.64
Total	66637.68	99689.02	220711.39

Export Performance by Export Oriented Units (EOUs) and Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Units of India (1992-1993 to 2012-2013-up to June, 2012)						
Year	SEZ Units		EOUs		Total	
	Rs. in Crore	In US\$ Million	Rs. in Crore	In US\$ Million	Rs. in Crore	In US\$ Million
1992-93	1376.31	474	2170.14	748	3546.45	1222
1993-94	1959.91	632	3086	995	5045.91	1627
1994-95	2653.11	856	4709.59	1519	7362.7	2375
1995-96	3235.63	981	7009.36	2123	10244.99	3104
1996-97	4338.92	1240	8728.72	2494	13067.64	3734
1997-98	4817.3	1302	10278.51	2778	15095.81	4080
1998-99	5252.48	1250	12058.27	2871	17310.75	4121
1999-00	6708.62	1560	13701.29	3186	20409.91	4746
2000-01	8449.04	1878	15912	3536	24361.04	5414
2001-02	9200.42	1957	18735.45	3930.11	27935.87	5887.11
2002-03	10056.62	2095	23590.6	4874.56	33647.22	6969.56
2003-04	13813.58	2996	28827.58	6273.51	42641.16	9269.51
2004-05	18655	4140	37488.38	8343.45	56143.38	12483.45
2005-06	22840	4984	49462.35	8505.69	59967.18	13489.69
2006-07	34787	-	69964.6	-	-	-
2007-08	66638	-	168838.78	-	-	-
2008-09	99689	-	176923.02	-	-	-
2009-10	220712	-	84135.66	-	-	-
2010-11	315868	-	40260.20*	-	-	-
2011-12	364477.73	-	-	-	-	-
2012-13#	118321.56	-	-	-	-	-

Note : * : April-September, 2010.

: April-June, 2012.

Source : Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Govt. of India. (10673),
(11466), (12485),
Rajya Sabha Unstarred Question No. 333, dated on 03.08.2011,
Lok Sabha Starred Question No. 351, dated on 30.04.2012 &
Rajya Sabha Unstarred Question No. 10, dated on 08.08.2012.

Export Performance of EOUs Vs India Exports			
(1996-1997 to 2011-2012)			
(Rs. in Crore)			
Year	EOUs Exports	India's Exports	EOUs Share in
			India's Export % age
1996-97	8728.72	118817	10.99
1997-98	10278.51	130101	7.9
1998-99	12058.27	139753	8.63
1999-00	13701.29	159561	8.59
2000-01	15912	203571	7.82
2001-02	18743.45	209018	8.97
2002-03	23590.6	255137	9.25
2003-04	28827.58	293367	9.83
2004-05	39228.4	375340	10.45
2005-06	49462.35	456418	10.84
2006-07	69964.6	571779	12.24
2007-08	163838.78	655864	24.98
2008-09	176923.02	840755	21.04
2009-10	71083.27	845125	8.41
2010-11	76031.13	1142922	6.65
2011-12	54032*	1023856*	5.27

Note : * : Upto December, 2011.

Source : EOU India, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Govt. of India. (ON35),
Lok Sabha Starred Question No. 278, dated on 29.11.2010,
Rajya Sabha Unstarred Question No. 336, dated on 03.08.2011. &
Lok Sabha Unstarred Question No. 6176, dated on 14.05.2012.

Abbreviations:

FSEZ : Falta Special Economic Zone.

NSEZ : Noida Special Economic Zone.

VSEZ : Visakhapatnam Special Economic Zone.

SEEP-SEZ : Santacruz Electronics Export Processing Zone-Special Economic Zone.

MSEZ : Mumbai Special Economic Zone.

CSEZ : Cochin Special Economic Zone.

KASEZ : Kandla Special Economic Zone.

SEZ-wise Export Performance (In Rs.) of Operational Export Oriented Units in India								
(2005-2006 to 2008-2009)								
(Value : Rs. in Crore)								
Jurisdictional SEZs	Export (Value : Rs. in Crore)				Percentage Growth			Units in Operation (As on 31.3.2009)
	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09 (P)	006-07/ 005-06	2007-08 /2006-07	008-09 /2007-08	
NSEZ	8615.5	10546.77	10764.64	10848	2.42	2.07	.77	418
SEEPZ-SEZ	8293.73	11900.09	19912.4	14303	3.48	67.33	28.17	464
MSEZ	7557.91	13590.97	15651.38	8766.76	9.82	15.16	43.99	493
CSEZ	15943.17	18834.55	21404.24	15711.45	8.14	13.64	26.6	511
VSEZ	2676.82	4366.62	7167.69	8944.69	3.13	64.15	4.79	238
FSEZ	1658.79	2509.95	2647.57	2265.49	1.31	5.48	14.43	103
KASEZ	4716.43	7420.88	90405.78	102269.79	7.34	1118.26	3.12	301
ISEZ		794.77	885.08	1043		11.36	7.84	18
Total	49462.35	69964.6	168838.8	164152.2	1.45	141.32	2.78	2546

Source : EOU India, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Govt. of India. (ON35)

Problems of SEZs

The problems of SEZs are studied in two perspectives- Firm's perspective and Investor's perspective .These problems may be the summarized as follows.

- The results show that the level of satisfaction for the availability of water is less than average in SEZs. However, 48% of the respondents were found to have been arranging water from outside the zones.
- Power availability is rated satisfactory or more than satisfactory by a majority of the respondents in the zones across country.
- Transport facilities are rated low in almost all SEZs. Transport facilities within the zones are almost nonexistent in all SEZs and hence are below average. Poor and congested roads sharply increase the time for transporting the containers to and fro the port. This also resulted in time loss for the labour.
- Indian ports are also stated to be characterized by delays and inefficiencies
- Communication facilities have been considered to be the most satisfactory of all the infrastructure facilities. Given the information revolution taking place in country, it is not surprising.

Apparently, overall quality of infrastructure in the zones is considered above average in all SEZs. And there are no remarkable variations across the selected SEZs. However, infrastructure out side to the zones such as roads and ports, are not found to be adequate in general.

Governance

Factor analysis yielded four broad factors within which our questions could be grouped. These are:

- Transparency,
- Effectiveness of the authorities in providing services,
- Simplification of the rules, and
- Attitude of the officials

Two important observations have been made. First, the quality of governance in general is almost the average of 2.5 in almost all the SEZs. Second, the 'Simplification of the rules' scored the lowest, suggesting that the rules in SEZs are complex and leads to delays in bureaucratic decisions.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The consensus in India seems to be that the country is now on the right track and has just about started in ascension to richness – there is even a claim by the last president that India can become a developed country by 2020 (Kalam and Rajan, 1998). The current economic growth, combined with a huge population will surely make India a very important player, but there is still a long way before the population can enjoy anything like the living standards of western countries and some of their East Asian and Southeast Asian neighbors.

Our government at the moment cannot provide that level of infrastructure, which is crucial for growth and ultimately making India an economic power much in the lines of China. So the best way out of this situation is to build huge clusters of industrial activities which are well connected via land, sea and air along with their complete set of infrastructural facilities viz. own power generation plant, water supply, etc. This way the whole country may not be propelled into the era of excellence but at least these zones would surely become centers of excellence themselves and propel economic growth of the country.

Researcher would like to emphasize that SEZs have to be designed very carefully and that a number of aspects have to be considered. Especially, the political decision-maker must be careful in choosing the right mixture of the policy instrument. Wei Ge (1999) formulates this as: "A successful SEZ operation depends critically on a set of economic and institutional factors."

On the basis of analysis and findings, researcher puts forward the following suggestions to policy makers, promoters of SEZs and units in SEZs so that the SEZs may fulfill their objectives for which they were started.

- An international harbour / airport should be close by SEZ or at least the possibility for such a development in the near future should exist, till than dry-port facility should be provided to each SEZ.
- Objectives, for which SEZs have been established, should be reviewed time to time with all political parties according to changing economic needs of country.
- It would be good for SEZs to develop larger areas not just small enclaves, as done in case of EPZs earlier in country.
- The sectors, in which foreign engagement is allowed, should be carefully chosen. As the analysis of the study has demonstrated, especially those sectors should be chosen which have a strong backward linkage effect for the whole country.

- The investment of domestic enterprises has to be controlled so that the SEZs do not have a distortionary effect on the regional development. Domestic firms should be checked to relocate in the SEZs just because of the preferential treatment.
- There must be an activity chart regarding the development of a SEZ which should be made public in detail.
- It is important that the investors of SEZs should find the entire infrastructure of international standard at reasonable price such as international telephone lines, water, electricity supply, public transportation, insurance, ports, banks and forwarding companies, etc.
- The results of this study show that factors, like the growth potential, the quality of the infrastructure, the political stability are much more important to decide the inflow of foreign investment. Thus, the government must be careful in not overestimating the possible influence of tax privileges on the investment decision of foreign investors.
- Incentives must be to meet out the initial establishing expenditure to foreign investors taking place due to the new environment and other cost increasing factors. But the incentives must not be for the investment decision only, because in that case, the investors will start to think about moving out from the host country as soon as the incentives are abolished.
- Research and training institutions should be planned for providing skilled/semi - skilled workers from the beginning so that the potential for a further development exist.
- The legal system should be to protect the intellectual property rights of investors of SEZs. Otherwise the foreign investors will avoid transferring their latest technology if they are not protected against copying their knowledge/ technology.
- The customs authorities should be included in the design of the SEZ from the beginning for necessary customs clearance.
- Convertibility of the domestic currency including capital-account convertibility for foreign investors is an important factor that influences the investment decision of foreign investors and should therefore be taken into account from the beginning of the planning process.
- The government should try to sign investment guarantee agreements with other countries or the country should become member of the Convention on Settlement of Investment Disputes, because this gives foreign investors the feeling that their engagement is protected by international agreements.
- An effective and flexible administration, based on a transparent and consistent legal framework can reduce the costs of businesses substantially. A local advisory body should be established to help foreign investors to get easy and reliable information for orientation. It should provide information on labour recruitment, wage regulations, for helping to establish good relations.
- SEZs should fulfill their social responsibilities in broader sense. SEZs should recruit and train local individuals, especially those have sacrificed their land in development of SEZs.
- SEZs should attract and promote foreign investment through Indian Diaspora.

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